

Sea ice classification of the Hornsund fjord using RADARSAT-2 and Sentinel-1 imagery from 2012 to 2016

JULLIAN C.B. WILLIAMS[†], ZUZANNA M. SWIRAD[†]

[†] Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland
64 Księcia Janusza St. 01-452 Warsaw, Poland

*corresponding author : jullian.williams@igf.edu.pl

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Abstract

Sentinel-1 and RADARSAT-2 are synthetic aperture radar (SAR) imagers that allow unprecedented, high resolution monitoring of Arctic sea ice areas. The SAR imagery is used in this study to classify sea ice in the Hornsund fjord and the adjacent portion of the Greenland Sea with a support vector machine (SVM) classifier. The classification scheme allows an automated process of creating artificial data, applying segmentation, using an automatic reclassifying process from geometric substructures in the fjord and finally, outputting both a multi-classed and binary classed fjord ice area result. From this, a time series analysis of sea ice area and coverage through-out seasonal variation from 2012 to 2016, when both imagers have overlapping image temporal coverage. Finally, geostatistical measures are used to investigate the results of the support vector machine (SVM) method with the results of an existing gaussian classifier from binary sea ice/open water area maps.

keywords: Principal Component Analysis, sea ice, Hornsund fjord, Sentinel-1, RADARSAT-2, geoscience engineering, cryosphere science

I. INTRODUCTION

Sea ice coverage in the Hornsund fjord consists of varying ice types that dominate the scene given the season and location. Changes in the sea ice area governs the potential change in geophysical factors such as heat and gaseous exchanges (Delille, 2014), polar navigation (Lasserre, 2015) and water mass distribution (Prominska et al, 2018). To understand and map these changes, it is common place to use various methods and datasets to classify sea ice. Ressel et al. (2015) describes the use of a neural network based classification method using X-band SAR data. Other methods include the use of artificial neural net-

works to predict Arctic sea ice concentration (Choi et al., 2019), while Bij de Vaate et al.(2022) employs a commonly used method of thresholding and machine learning to classify sea ice leads. Lohse et al., (2019) used decision tree methods for sea ice classification while ice and open water classification with a gaussian classifier were used by Johansson et al. (2020) and Swirad et al. (2024). The use of Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrices (GLCM) or artificial data in tandem with a support vector machine method is typical and used in feature detection processes as described by Kurniati et al. (2024) and in (J Williams, 2024, unpublished data) where sea ice leads are detected and classified for a time series analysis, particularly in

the Beaufort Sea in the latter. The data used is important, especially during polar night time, where optical imagers are not able to image the ice surface due to cloud coverage and minimal sunlight. Therefore, it is common place to use synthetic aperture imagery to view sea ice scenes during polar-night, since this remote sensing instrumentation is not inhibited by cloud cover. The RADARSAT-2 and Sentinel-1 imagers are useful since these instruments are able to view the scene regardless of weather conditions and time of year. The instruments are C-band imagers that operate between 4-8 Gigahertz (Ghz), however, the temporal coverage and imaging modes differ. Sentinel-1 is a twin constellation consisting of S1A and S1B instruments that were launched on 2014 and 2016 respectively and is always right-looking. The RADARSAT-2 instrument was launched in 2007 and has both a right and left looking instrument. In the case of Sentinel-1 this study uses the extra-wide swath mode, which is recommended for sea ice scenes (Potin, 2013). The RADARSAT-2 data used ScanSAR narrow and ScanSAR wide swath modes. The nominal spatial resolution of the SAR images are 25-, 50- and 40- m for RADARSAT-2 ScanSAR narrow, wide and Sentinel-1 imagers respectively. However, all images are resampled at the 50m resolution for data consistency. The data available from both imagers are HH (co-polarized) and HV (cross-polarized) data. This allows analysis across imagers to be consistent in training sampling for the image classification process.

This paper uses a support vector machine method with artificially created data through Gray Level Co-Occurrence Matrices (GLCMs) in a python environment. Hornsund has ongoing monitoring that requires a systematic ice classification scheme that can be applied in other fjords in Svalbard. The process uses the co- and cross-polarized data to create gray levels which encapsulates information about the polarized scenes. Lohse (2021) and (J Williams, 2024, unpublished data) describe the most suitable combination of GLCMs for the purpose of classifying sea ice features using C-band SAR imagery. From this artificial information,

stacked images are used to sample and train the algorithm based on seasonal changes in the scene. The training data is used in the segmentation process through the support vector machine (SVM). This provides a first multi-class, vector output of the images. Geometric segments of the Hornsund fjord and Greenland Sea are then separated spatially by each bay, the main Hornsund basin and the available area of the Greenland Sea in the images. This allows the SVM segmented output to be reclassified by way of a regional rule based system. In this rule based system, each quadrant is given conditions to decide on the class of ice based on the initial segmentation, and then the location, shape and orientation of the detected object. Based on the condition, the initial ice class can be automatically reclassified to the correct ice type. This results in a multi-classed, as well as a binary classed output available for time series information.

The information derived from the two imagers results in data from 2012 to 2016. The binary classed images from the gaussian segmentation process described by Swirad et al. (2024) are compared to the binary classes derived from the SVM process. We use a Fourier transform method to analyse this data in the time domain to examine the difference in the amplitude of the signal each year from either method.

II. STUDY AREA

The Hornsund fjord is located in southwestern Spitsbergen, Svalbard, and opens to the Greenland in the West. The fjord is approximately 30 km long with a main basin and secondary bays. The total study area consists of the Hornsund fjord, which is 2.6×10^8 m² and includes the bays Brepollen, Burgbukta, Isbjornhamna, Samarinvagen and terminally, the Greenland Sea. Details of the geomorphology of the fjord is described by Swirad (2024) and Herman et al. (2025) suggests that the depth of the fjord is on average 100 m but extends to 250 m in the main basin. Figure 1 illustrates the constituents

Figure 1: *The Hornsund fjord in Svalbard adapted from Swirad et al., 2024*

of the Hornsund Fjord and its surrounding geographies.

The fjord is oriented in an east-west direction and is the southernmost fjord of West Spitsbergen, Svalbard with a complex bathymetry. Several ice types are found in Hornsund depending on the season as well as local and regional ocean and weather conditions. This includes drift, glacier and landfast ice types (Z Swirad, 2025, unpublished data). Calving events within marine-terminating glaciers deposit brecciated ice into the fjord in a scree-like, mass wasting manner which accumulate by the coast in shallower bays. Landfast and drifting ice are more present in the eastern bays of the Hornsund. The pack ice carried into Hornsund from the Barents Sea is proponent with respect to wind and wave conditions which are characterized by strong seasonal, interannual and daily scales.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

i. Sentinel-1.

Sentinel-1 is a dual instrument satellite that was launched in 2014 and 2016 for S1A/1B respectively. The imager is a C-band synthetic aperture radar (SAR) constellation with dual, co-and cross-polarization capabilities across the globe. In this study, we use the HH and HV bands to classify fjord ice. Sentinel-1 operates in various modes, such as the Interferometric

(IW), Extra-Wide Swath (EW), Wave (WV) and Stripmap (SM) mode. The European Space Agency recommends using the EW mode for open sea ice scenes (Potin, 2013). However, while the other modes can be used, modes such as the IW mode are recommended for on-land scenes. Nevertheless, the S1A and S1B instruments have a 6-day revisit period and 12-day crossover, either ascending or descending, providing an unprecedented look of sea ice surfaces in the Arctic. The EW images consist of five (5) sub-swath images whose total swath width is 410 km with a 40 m pixel resolution. The Sentinel-1 images used in this study are all speckle and ground-range corrected (including resolved to sigma-naught) and resampled to 50 m resolution for consistency between classification of the Sentinel-1 and RADARSAT-2 datasets.

ii. RADARSAT-2

The RADARSAT-2 constellation is a left and right looking instrument that launched in 2007. This instrument is also a C-band frequency imager that includes a radar receiver and down-link transmitter. Imaging modes available through RADARSAT-2 include Spotlight, Fine, Extra Fine, Wide, Extra Wide, Extended High and several others. However, in this study, we use the ScanSAR narrow and ScanSAR wide modes at 25- and 50 m pixel spacing at 300- and 500 km nominal swath widths, respectively. However, the ScanSAR narrow images, similar to the forementioned Sentinel-1 images, are resampled to match the 50 m resolutions in the wide mode. The images used from RADARSAT-2 in this study are also radiometrically and ground-range corrected to minimize noise and produce consistent image classification results. Similar to the Sentinel-1 imager, the RADARSAT-2 imager is capable of dual polarizations and even quadruple polarizations of image scenes. However, dual polarizations of co- and cross-polarized images are used (HH and HV) as with the Sentinel-1 data for both consistency of results and as a result of availability.

iii. Classification method

a. Gray level co-occurrence matrices (GLCMs) artificial data for Support Vector Machine Algorithm.

The gray level co-occurrence matrices (GLCMs) used in the study are used based on recommended processes in the support vector machine algorithm with the classification of sea ice. Indeed, there are several GLCMs that can be utilized such as variance, dissimilarity, contrast, homogeneity, etc. However, in the process of classification of ice areas, it is consistently recommended in several studies (Hird, et al., 2017; Lohse, et al., 2019; Fauzi, et al., 2020 ; J Williams, 2024, unpublished data) that the combination of gray levels to be used in such an algorithm are the variance, contrast, entropy and angular second moment (ASM). These are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Variance} &= \sum_{i,j=1}^N P_{i,j} (i - \mu_i)^2 \\ &\& \sum_{i,j=1}^N P_{i,j} (i - \mu_j)^2 \\ \text{Contrast} &= \sum_{i,j=1}^N P_{i,j} (i - j)^2 \\ \text{Entropy} &= \sum_{i,j=1}^N P_{i,j} (-\ln(P_{i,j})) \\ \text{ASM} &= \sum_{i,j=1}^N P_{i,j}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Where P is the probability of the matrix, (i,j), in which the pixel value μ is the mean pixel value of the matrix (Fausi, et al., 2020). The ice classes are visually inspected and labelled with visual aid from the Sentinel-2 images. This, along with the resultant texture features provide our training sample for our support vector machine learning technique. Open water and thin ice leads are separated using their elongated features, compared with other features that do not result from deformational forces. The training and test image ratio is 40-60% for which, the image composites are classified using the support vector machine classifier.

The support vector machine uses regression lines to create a decision boundary for each ice class. As the mean and standard deviation changes, a new ice class is created within the confines of the number of classes defined by

the user. Therefore, the SVM can be applied to both linear and non-linear data but the SVM expression does vary depending on the kernel (Mehrkanoon et al. 2012). A general equation can describe a dual objective function for a decision boundary as:

$$y(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i K(x, x_i) + b$$

Where α_i are the Lagrangian multipliers with the i-th training sample. $K(x, x_i)$ is the kernel function that computes the similarity between the points x and x_i . The variable b is defined by an explicitly known feature map or a weighting vector. The SVM therefore decides on each class based on given inputs, whose boundary definitions are determined at each inflection point of the regression line. These GLCMs provide texture measures that describe the ice surface in detail. This allows increased accuracy in the classification of fjord ice types with respect to the backscatter intensity. The algorithm uses the HH and HV bands to calculate the GLCMs described. This process allows a fourteen (14) band image composite for each day and whose training data points include the texture information necessary in the support vector machine classifier. The predicted data is fed into a vectorized shapefile where the first phase of geometric quantification can begin. That is, the area, perimeter, orientation and object roundness are calculated for each ice type in the fjord's scene.

b. Geometric substructure of the Hornsund fjord.

The Hornsund fjord and it's adjacent areas consist of glacier outflows or bays, a main basin area, as well as a segment of the Greenland Sea. In order to apply a secondary re-classification step that allows a geomorphological input of ice types in the fjord, information about the orientation and roundness of features in the fjord area is necessary as illustrated in Figure 2.

In this step, the fjord is sectioned in quadrants. This means that the latitude and longitude information for each bay, the main basin

Figure 2: Regional rule based system for geometric sub-structuring of the Hornsund fjord.

and Hornsund area, as well as the Greenland Sea area is generated to focus on the ice type features that occur in each area. Fast ice aligns itself parallel to the coast and headlands of the fjord. That is, fast ice is typically a lenticular and therefore oriented, usually in the North-South direction. Meanwhile, glacier ice deposits are scree-like in nature, with a more rounded or lobate shape. In the case of glacier deposits, there is no typically strong directional properties of glacier ice, but may drift as the brecciated ice moves from the bay area and into the main basin. Therefore, in both cases, we select a property of shape-wise separation of ice objects in the scene by defining roundness greater than or less than 0.6 for rounded and lenticular objects, respectively.

In order to capture the drift ice areas, we separate the Greenland Sea, main basin and Hornsund areas from the entire area of study. This results in definitions of ice types with respect to the initial classification result that is re-classified based on a regional rule based system in the fjord.

The image composites are classified based on winter and summer training data, demarcated

with the use of optical images (Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8) through-out the timeline of the data. This means, that the seasons are trained based on consecutive ice days (Winter) and consecutive ice-free days (Summer) in the fjord. This provides a seasonal classified image product in Hornsund from 2012 to 2016. In this particular study, to compare the results from the SVM method with the gaussian method described by Swirad et al. (2024), the multi-class results are converted to a binary class result. That is, an ice and water binary classified product for the time series analysis. To compare the results, geostatistical measures are used. Specifically a principal component analysis, which describes the variance of the results between methods, as well as a Fourier transform method to investigate the results in the frequency domain and reconstruct the data to compare them in the time domain. These measures exemplify the differences and similarities in the methods used and explain the robustness of the support vector machine method used to classify fjord ice.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The time series analysis includes the total sea ice area across the Hornsund fjord and it's adjacent features from 2012 to 2016. The support vector machine and gaussian methods show the change in the ice area over time through-out the seasons. Figure 3 shows the total ice area from both methods through the years described.

The figure shows the change in ice area by each month, showing the seasonality of ice coverage with the changing seasons. This cyclical behaviour of the ice cover is illustrated and the variance in the ice area is further described using correlation matrices, shown in Figure 4. The figure shows an inverse relationship between the total ice-water areas in the SVM and gaussian methods on a monthly scale. The SVM and gaussian classification schemes describe an ice-water relationship where, as the ice area increases, the water area decreases

Figure 3: Total ice area in squared-meters in Hornsund from 2012-2016 from the Gaussian and Support Vector Machine methods.

and vice versa with changing conditions and movement of ice in the fjord. However, this relationship changes on a yearly scale. The SVM method shows a strong, direct relationship between ice-water areas through-out time while the gaussian method shows a strong, inverse relationship.

The yearly correlation matrices suggests that ice and water areas from the gaussian method describe the fjord area as increasingly water dominated or increasingly ice dominated with changing conditions. The yearly correlation from the SVM method on the other hand suggests an ice area that is spatially defined where, as the ice area increases in a segment of the fjord, the water area dominates in other segments of the fjord. The SVM method may describe the movement of ice in the fjord on monthly and yearly scales. For example, the increase in the ice area from the production of fast ice and drift ice is strongly correlated between October through-out June. During this time, the variance of the ice in the fjord is described largely by this production and movement of ice in the fjord and as this ice is transported and consolidated, the available water in the fjord decreases as melting conditions increase in the Summer. This is also

explained by the production of more dominant glacier ice, which is more present during the Summer-Autumn cycle allowing more ice to be transported in the bays during the melting season.

On the yearly scale, the SVM suggests that the ice type available through-out time may coincide with increasing availability of water in the fjord. That is, the type of ice dominat-

Figure 4: Monthly (A) and yearly (B) correlation heatmaps of ice and water classes derived from the Support Vector Machine method. and monthly (C) and yearly (D) correlation heatmaps of ice and water classes derived from the Gaussian method.

ing the fjord area may be more terrigenous in nature (glacier ice) and more available throughout the year. However, the gaussian method may suggest that the ice-water relationship continues to show defined and specific cycles of water areas as ice regresses. The opposite is true from the SVM method which may suggest a change in the ice coverage and type over time, subjugating the fraction of water coverage. Further investigation of the variance in the classification schemes is examined by using a principal component analysis (PCA). The first and second components describe the majority of the variance in the ice covered areas. In this study, we use the first three components from the methods with respect to time. Figure 5 shows the correlation matrix between the methods, with respect to time (in julian day) for the components mentioned.

The first component shows a strong and very strong, direct relationship with the SVM and gaussian methods and a strongly inverse relationship with the julian day, each year. In the second component, a very strong, direct relationship exists with the SVM method. A weak inverse relationship with the gaussian method, but a strong, positive relationship with julian day correlates with the second component as well. The third component shows a weak relationship with the SVM method but very strongly positive relationships in the Gaussian method and julian day. The principal components that describe the most variance in the data shows strong, positive relationships with the SVM and gaussian methods and an inverse relationship with progressive days of the year. However, the SVM method appears to be fully described by the two most defining components of the ice area's variance. Still, the gaussian method appears to still encompass the variance described by the later, third component. The results of the principal component analysis and correlations suggest that the variance between the methods used may be as a result of differences that are not entirely temporal since either method display strong relationships on the daily, monthly and yearly scales. It is important to note in the method

Figure 5: Correlation heatmap of the first three principal components with the ice areas derived from the Support Vector Machine and Gaussian methods and Julian day.

Figure 6a: Difference of means between January and February from the Support Vector Machine and Gaussian methods.

used in the gaussian classification, sometimes both the HH and HV bands are not used. The method described suggests that the HV band is sometimes removed to improve the results of their classification method. However, the HV band gives vital information about the noise floor and can be a critical component in ice class separation, especially in the cases where newly formed ice types (e.g. nilas) are considered. Still, the PCA suggests that there is general agreement between the methods with their concurring direct relationships. However, the difference in the methods used may be spatially related. Figure 6 shows difference maps of the January to February ice area from the SVM and gaussian methods. Here, the difference of the means, standard deviations, median and sums are illustrated.

The mean and standard deviations from the

Figure 6b: Difference of standard deviations between January and February from the Support Vector Machine and Gaussian methods.

Figure 6c: Difference of medians between January and February from the Support Vector Machine and Gaussian methods.

methods show greater differences within the Hornsund and Greenland Sea areas. The SVM method shows defined differences in the bays, especially within Brepollen and the Northern Greenland Sea areas, while the gaussian method shows more difference in the more southerly segment of the Greenland Sea. Overall, the mean and standard deviation shows more difference in the more open sea area, where drifting ice is allowed to freely circulate. In contrast, the Brepollen area and its surrounding bays show greater differences in the glacier and fast ice dominant sections. This is particularly visible in the SVM method over Burgerbukta where ice may be allowed to enter the bay and accumulate fast ice. The gaussian method however, does not show this spatial relationship with the exception of a larger difference displayed along the western edge of Brepollen. In Samarinvagen, both methods show a defined difference of means, however on this is prominent on the western edge of the bay in the gaussian method. The SVM method however, shows a marked difference all along the edge of the bay where ice may be allowed to migrate from one edge of the bay to the other with movement in ocean circulation and wind activity.

The difference in medians describes almost no difference in the Greenland Sea area, but major differences concentrated in the Brepollen and generally eastern section of the map area. While the SVM method shows more of its differences along the bay edge, the gaussian method shows a defined, negative difference in its ice area. This is in direct contrast of the dif-

Figure 6d: Difference of sums between January and February from the Support Vector Machine and Gaussian methods.

ference in means where the eastern section of the map area showed approximately no difference. Indeed, this contrast is also true for the SVM method, where the difference of means showed more defined changes in the ice area in the same segment. The difference in medians may therefore describe the sections in which the ice may be described as more static, with the gaussian method suggesting that the areas of ice accumulation do not move about freely in the fjord while the SVM method suggests an ice field that static ice is concentrated specifically along the headlands and bays of the fjord. The difference in sums show the fjord ice area with a greater and more extensive differences in the SVM method than the gaussian method. The ice area in the gaussian method shows greater difference just along the edge of the western Brepollen area, the northern edge of the Greenland Sea and Hornsund areas, as well as the western Samarinvagen sections. However, the SVM method shows a larger difference in the sums all across the fjord.

The SVM method shows a difference along the corridor which ice is allowed to enter the

Figure 7: Fourier transform of ice signal from the Support Vector Machine and Gaussian methods into the time domain from 2012-2016.

fjord through the Greenland Sea. The channelling of ice in and out of the fjord is defined in these areas from the Greenland Sea and into Hornsund and accumulating along the edges of the bays of the fjord through longshore drift. However, the gaussian method does not show this definition in movement, but instead shows defined differences in ice accumulation only in these edge-wise sections of the fjord. The lesser defined differences are shown towards the Greenland Sea area in the gaussian method as well. Still, the gaussian method suggests an increase in ice in the bays in February, contrasting the SVM method which illustrates peak accumulation of ice in the fjord in January, at the height of winter. Finally, we use a Fourier analysis to transform the data into the frequency domain and reconstruct the results throughout the years. This is shown in Figure 7, where the reconstructed, yearly ice signal is produced for both methods.

The results of the Fourier show general agreement between the data’s signal throughout time. The figure shows two defined peaks in 2013 and 2015 from the gaussian method.

This relationship is shown in the SVM method as well, but at a lower amplitude. Nevertheless, the yearly cycles show a near dual-crested cycle with peaks at 2013 and 2015 from both methods. The gaussian method illustrates a more defined peak in 2013 and agrees with the strongly defined peak in 2015 and gradual decrease into 2016. The results suggest that while there are differences in the outputs from each method, there is general agreement with the changes in the ice coverage in the fjord. The time series analysis shows that the difference in outputs may lay specifically with the framework of the algorithms and the backscatter intensity signatures during classification. The difference in describing ice from water is a critical component that the HV band is integral for. That is, the difference in describing the ice in the field is juxtaposed by the algorithms ability to separate the areas that are transitional and capture the evolution of ice in the fjord. Thinner ice that is allowed to congeal and consolidate to form the fjord’s sea ice, as well as the movement of glacier ice across and out of the bays is difficult, but is better informed with the use of more polarizing bands.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The support vector machine method has demonstrated its ability to produce ice classification results on par with the gaussian method in comparison. Of course, the results of both methods show some variance, which may be strongly attributed to specific choices in the algorithm building where in the gaussian method, inconsistent use of the HV band can affect the backscatter intensity in the signal for the ice scene classification. Still, the SVM and gaussian method show similar trends in the ice area despite differences in training and data compilation.

This might also suggest that the difference in methods are underpinned by the individual ice types. That is, the multi-classed ice types (glacier, landfast and drift ice) aggregated into binary ice maps, which may be further denoted

by consistent use of the HV band. This is particularly useful since the pixelwise change in the ice scene governs consistent classification of ice which can be largely indistinct in SAR data. Of course, ice in a SAR scene can be ambiguous. The separation of newer ice types such as nilas and grease ice is particularly important since, depending on the conditions, can appear to be water. Thin ice types can also appear as ridges or rafted ice if windy conditions exist. Therefore, consistent use of the HV band is paramount in discriminating ice types which can invariably describe the scene with more accuracy with more information of noise in the image scene. This, coupled with further texture information provide a robust look at the features in the ice scene for a better classification result. This allows for time series data that demonstrates a variance that is representative of the true ice signal throughout time.

VI. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

JW was the primary producer of the study, processed and analyzed all the data. ZS contributed to the editing and discussion of the study.

VII. FUNDING

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VIII. CODE AVAILABILITY

This code corresponding with this paper can be found at this link.

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